

Practice Abstract no. 39

Promoting institutional and industry collaboration for trust and transparency in data sharing

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

Building on the findings of the workshop and breakout room sessions, the following recommendation and driving actions was proposed:

Recommendation: Foster collaboration among institutions and industry to enable a culture of trust and transparency in data sharing.

Proposed Actions:

- 1. Develop standardised and/ or review (existing) data sharing protocols:** Data sharing faces two main obstacles: issues with how data is collected and stored, and a general lack of interoperability. To address this, it is crucial to improve data integrity and interoperability by either developing new standardised protocols or thoroughly reviewing existing ones, particularly regarding how similar data types are stored (e.g., formats and naming conventions).
- 2. Implement trustworthy data platforms:** To ensure trust and transparency in data sharing, all entities processing data must use secure and privacy-preserving data platforms. These are essential for offering robust access control and comprehensive audit trails. Citizens must also be empowered to easily access their information through user-friendly and clear interfaces and communication channels..
- 3. Facilitate "Win-Win" scenarios for food system actors:** Defining tangible incentives is crucial to encourage broader participation in data sharing, creating 'win-win' scenarios for all stakeholders. This is especially vital for small-scale actors, such as farmers, who might lack motivation to engage. For the industry, benefits could include new product development opportunities or a competitive edge, while consumers might receive personalised services, such as health advice.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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